

Isolation of Bergein from *Saxifraga Ligulata* Wall

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Roots of *Saxifraga ligulata* Wall (syn. *Bergenia ligulata* Wall) (Hindi name: 'Pashanbhedā') of the Family *Saxifragaceae* are highly reputed in the indigenous systems of medicine, especially for their efficacy in dissolving stones in the kidney¹.

Extraction of the finely powdered roots (400 g.) successively with light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) and ether in a Soxhlet extractor afforded light brown residues (ca. 0.75 and 0.55% respectively). Further extraction of the residual drug with ethanol (95%) furnished a dark red extract, which gave, on evaporation in *vacuo*, a dark red gummy residue 'A' (ca. 35% on the basis of powdered roots). The tannin and the non-tannin materials present in 'A' were separated by the conventional 'lead acetate' method. The aqueous filtrate containing the non-tannin portion was concentrated on a water bath to provide a syrupy residue 'B' which was crystallised from methanol as fine, colorless needles (total yield 2.4g., 0.6%). Three more crystallisations gave the pure compound 'JS', m.p. 237-38° (after drying in high vacuum at 80° for several hours). (Found: C, 48.21, 48.38; H, 4.84, 5.12; N, nil; active H, 4.58. $C_{14}H_{18}O_{10}$ requires C, 48.56; H, 5.24; 6 active H, 1.73; 5 active H, 1.44%). It had the following spectral absorptions. UV: $\lambda_{\max}^{EtOH}$ 272 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.90), showing a bathochromic shift to 309 m μ , on being made alkaline with aqueous NaOH. IR: $\nu_{\max}^{nujol}$ 3460 ('bonded' -OH), 1710 (-C=O, open chain or 6-m-ring), 1613, 1520, 1460 cm^{-1} (aromatic ring). It had no acidic properties, readily reduced Fehling's and Tollen's reagents but failed to give a semicarbazone or a 2, 4-DNP and did not give a positive Molisch test. On treatment with acetic anhydride and pyridine, it gave an acetate (crystallised from methanol), m.p. 207-208°; $\lambda_{\max}^{EtOH}$ 252 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.0); IR (nujol): 3500 (v. weak), 1785, 1750, 1613, 1574, 1472 cm^{-1} . [Found: C, 52.12; H, 4.67; active H, 0.30. $C_{14}H_{18}O_5$ (OAc)₃ requires C, 51.80; H, 5.07; 1 active H, 0.18; 2, active H, 0.35%). The remarkable changes in the UV and IR spectra (especially the -C=O stretching frequencies) in the acetylated compound, as compared with 'JS', are interesting though somewhat surprising. It also gave methyl ether on treatment with diazomethane (obtained from *N*-nitrosomethylurea) which could be crystallised from methanol-ethyl acetate; m.p. 190-200°.

Analytical and other data on the substance 'JS' and its derivatives, described above, suggest that the material 'JS' is probably identical with bergein² (I), a *C*-glycosyl compound that has been reported from diverse botanical sources³.

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1. Nudkarni, "Indian Materia Medica", Vol. I, 3rd ed., Popular Book Depot, Bombay, p. 1119.
2. Hay and Haynes, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2231; Posternak and Dürr, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 41, 1150.
3. Dean and Walker, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1958, 1696, and references cited therein.

Direct comparison of the m.p., behaviour, R_f values, ultraviolet, and infrared spectra of 'JS' with those of an authentic sample of bergenin, kindly supplied by Dr. J. Walker, National Institute for Medical Research, London, confirmed the correctness of our suggestion. The authentic bergenin (ex *Humiria balsamifera*) from London was crystallized by us from methanol under conditions identical with those used for the preparation of 'JS' before the comparison was actually made. The identity of 'JS' and bergenin was further confirmed by the undepressed mixed m.p.'s of their acetates and the methyl ethers prepared under identical conditions. The interesting spectral features of bergenin and its derivatives, referred to already, have been adequately commented upon by Hay and Haynes².

Work on the other fractions of *Saxifraga ligulata* is still in progress and will be reported in due course.

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